

September 5,
2025

JOURNAL OF
INTERNATIONAL SCIENCE
NETWORKS

SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

www.bestjournalup.com

Conference directions:

1. Scientific technologies
2. Economy
3. Biotechnology
4. Mathematical analysis
5. Technical sciences
6. Pedagogy
7. Psychology
8. Philosophy
9. History
10. Informatics

INDEXING

zenodo

OpenAIRE | EXPLORE

UDC: 001.891

International scientific and practical conference. International scientific and Applied Research. 05.09.2025.

In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

OILADA ZO‘RAVONLIK: ZO‘RAVONLIKNING OLDINI OLISH VA PSIXOSOTSIAL YORDAMNI TASHKIL ETISHGA FANLARARO YONDASHUV

Sunnatov Abbos Baxtiyor o‘g‘li

O‘zbekiston Milliy universitetining Jizzax filiali

Annotatsiya: Mazkur tezisda oiladagi zo‘ravonlikning ijtimoiy-psixologik mohiyati, uning turlari, sabablari hamda oqibatlari tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, zo‘ravonlikning oldini olishda psixologiya, sotsiologiya, huquqshunoslik va pedagogika fanlarining o‘zaro integratsiyasi asosida ishlab chiqilgan fanlararo yondashuvning ahamiyati yoritilgan. Tadqiqot oilaviy nizolarni erta aniqlash, psixosotsial yordamni tizimli tashkil etish hamda ijtimoiy institutlar o‘rtasidagi hamkorlikni kuchaytirish zarurligini asoslaydi.

Kalit so‘zlar: oila, zo‘ravonlik, psixosotsial yordam, profilaktika, fanlararo yondashuv, ijtimoiy himoya, psixologik maslahat.

Kirish

Bugungi kunda oiladagi zo‘ravonlik muammosi nafaqat ijtimoiy, balki psixologik, huquqiy va ma‘naviy jihatdan ham eng dolzarb masalalardan biri sifatida ko‘rilmog‘da. Jamiyatning barqaror rivojlanishi, inson huquqlarining ta‘minlanishi va sog‘lom ijtimoiy muhitning shakllanishi, eng avvalo, oilada tinchlik va totuvlikning ta‘minlanishiga bog‘liqdir. Shu bois, oilaviy zo‘ravonlikka qarshi kurashish va uning oldini olish davlat siyosati hamda fuqarolik jamiyati institutlarining muhim yo‘nalishlaridan biri hisoblanadi.

Oila — bu shaxsning birlamchi ijtimoiylashuv makoni, unda insonning qadriyatlari, xulq-atvori, ijtimoiy roli shakllanadi. Ammo oila ichidagi zo‘ravonlik insonning ruhiy, jismoniy va ijtimoiy holatiga jiddiy zarar yetkazadi, ijtimoiy aloqalarni izdan chiqaradi va jamiyatning umumiy farovonligiga tahdid soladi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, zo‘ravonlikka uchragan shaxslarning aksariyati ruhiy jarohat, o‘ziga ishonchsizlik, ijtimoiy faollikning pasayishi kabi muammolarga duch keladilar. Bu esa psixologik yordam va ijtimoiy qo‘llab-quvvatlashning tizimli tashkil etilishini taqozo etadi.

Oilaviy zo‘ravonlikni samarali bartaraf etish uchun **fanlararo yondashuv** zarur bo‘lib, bu yondashuv psixologiya, sotsiologiya, pedagogika, huquqshunoslik va tibbiyot kabi turli sohalar mutaxassislarining o‘zaro hamkorligini nazarda tutadi. Har bir fan o‘zining ilmiy-uslubiy imkoniyatlari orqali muammoning alohida jihatlarini o‘rganadi va amaliy yechimlar ishlab chiqadi. Psixologik yondashuv shaxsiy travmalarni bartaraf etishga xizmat qilsa, huquqiy yondashuv jabrlanuvchilarning huquq va manfaatlarini himoya qilishni ta‘minlaydi, pedagogik yondashuv esa profilaktika va ma‘rifat ishlarini tashkil etishga qaratilgan.

O‘zbekistonda ham so‘nggi yillarda oilaviy zo‘ravonlikka qarshi kurashish, ayollar va bolalarni himoya qilishga oid normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar qabul qilinib,

amaliy dasturlar yo‘lga qo‘yildi. Xususan, 2019-yilda “Xotin-qizlarni tazyiq va zo‘ravonlikdan himoya qilish to‘g‘risida”gi Qonun, 2019-yilda esa “Xotin-qizlar va erkaklar uchun teng huquq hamda imkoniyatlar kafolatlari to‘g‘risida”gi Qonun qabul qilinishi ushbu sohada muhim qadam bo‘ldi. Shu bilan birga, psixosotsial yordam markazlari, ishonch telefonlari, ijtimoiy reabilitatsiya dasturlari faoliyatini kengaytirish zarurati ham mavjud.

Shunday qilib, oilaviy zo‘ravonlikning oldini olish va jabrlangan shaxslarga samarali yordam ko‘rsatish masalasi **kompleks, fanlararo yondashuv asosida hal etilishi** lozim. Ushbu tadqiqotning dolzarbligi ham aynan shu zaruratdan kelib chiqadi — ya‘ni, oilaviy zo‘ravonlikni kamaytirish, uning psixologik, sotsiologik va huquqiy ildizlarini chuqur tahlil qilish, psixosotsial yordam tizimini takomillashtirish orqali sog‘lom va barqaror oilaviy muhitni shakllantirishdir.

Asosiy qism

Oila ichidagi zo‘ravonlikning shakllari — **jismoniy, ruhiy, iqtisodiy va jinsiy zo‘ravonlik** bo‘lib, ular shaxsning o‘zini qadsiz his etishiga, stress va depressiya holatlarining kuchayishiga olib keladi. Psixologik tadqiqotlar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, oilaviy zo‘ravonlik ko‘pincha kommunikatsiya yetishmasligi, stress, iqtisodiy tanglik va ijtimoiy qo‘llab-quvvatlash tizimining sustligi natijasida kelib chiqadi.

Zo‘ravonlikning oldini olishda **fanlararo yondashuv** quyidagi yo‘nalishlarni o‘z ichiga oladi:

- **Psixologik yo‘nalish:** oilaviy nizolarning erta diagnostikasi, individual va guruh terapiya o‘tkazish.
- **Sotsiologik yo‘nalish:** oiladagi rollar tizimini tahlil qilish, ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda zo‘ravonlikka qarshi targ‘ibot.
- **Huquqiy yo‘nalish:** himoya orderlari, qonuniy javobgarlik va davlat kafolatlarini kuchaytirish.
- **Pedagogik yo‘nalish:** o‘quvchilar, ota-onalar va pedagoglar o‘rtasida ma‘naviy-axloqiy tarbiya orqali profilaktika olib borish.

1-jadval.

Fanlararo yondashuvning asosiy yo‘nalishlari va natijalari

№	Yo‘nalish	Amalga oshiriladigan faoliyat	Kutilayotgan natija
1	Psixologik	Konsultatsiya, psixoterapiya	Ruhiy barqarorlikni tiklash
2	Sotsiologik	Oilaviy rollarni tahlil qilish	Oila ichidagi muloqotni yaxshilash
3	Huquqiy	Himoya orderlari, qonuniy javobgarlik	Zo‘ravonlik darajasining kamayishi
4	Pedagogik	Tarbiyaviy seminarlar, treninglar	Zo‘ravonlikka toqatsiz munosabat shakllanishi

Xulosa

Oiladagi zo‘ravonlikni kamaytirish va bartaraf etishda yagona bir yo‘l emas, balki **kompleks, fanlararo yondashuv** muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Psixologik yordam, ijtimoiy himoya, huquqiy chora-tadbirlar va tarbiyaviy ta’sir uyg‘unlikda amalga oshirilsa, jamiyatda sog‘lom oilaviy muhit shakllanadi. Shu tariqa, zo‘ravonlikning ildizini yo‘qotish emas, balki uni erta aniqlash va samarali psixosotsial yordam ko‘rsatish asosiy vazifa bo‘lishi kerak.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro‘yxati:

1. Abdumalikovna N. M. OILADA BOLALARNING IJTIMOIIY-EMOTSIONAL RIVOJLANISHIDA OTA-ONANING IJTIMOIIY ROLINI BAHOLASH //AMERICAN JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY BULLETIN. – 2025. – T. 3. – №. 8. – C. 33-39.
2. Kurbanbayevna Y. N. BOLALARGA NISBATAN OILA MUHITIDA KUZATILADIGAN ZO'RAVONLIK MUAMMOSI //Tadqiqotlar. – 2025. – T. 63. – №. 4. – C. 309-313.
3. Obidjonovna X. M. TAZYIQ VA ZO ‘RAVONLIKKA UCHRAGAN BOLALARGA PSIXOLOGIK YORDAM //Modern education and development. – 2025. – T. 35. – №. 2. – C. 374-383.
4. Mamatqulovna Y. M. BOLALARGA NISBATAN ZO’RAVONLIKKA CHEK QO‘YISHNING DOLZARB PSIXOLOGIK MASALALARI //Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi. – 2025. – T. 45. – №. 2. – C. 272-276.
5. Xudoyberdi o‘g‘li X. O. OTA-ONA VA FARZANDLAR O ‘RTASIDAGI NIZOLARNING IJTIMOIIY-PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI //Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari. – 2025. – T. 18. – №. 2. – C. 174-188.
6. Ibrohimovna Q. G. ZO’RAVONLIKKA QARSHI KURASHISHNING MUHIM VA DOLZARB MASALALARI //MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 33. – C. 13-16.